

(m, CH₃), 7.0–8.0 (ArH), 10.2 (OH) and 12.6 (SH). This shows that the ligands exists in thiol form rather than thione form, which supports the IR observation and non-involvement of proton on the sulfur in the reaction. The signals at δ 10.2 disappears in the spectra of the complexes, confirming that the hydroxy group has reacted with metal(II) moiety via deprotonation. The presence of a singlet at δ 12.6 suggests that in the complexes the ligands retains thiol form. The signal due to azomethine proton in the complex appears at δ 9.0. The downfield shift observed indicates the deshielding effect due to the coordination of nitrogen to the central metal ion.

The IR, PMR, conductance and analytical data suggest that coordination has taken place through azomethine nitrogen as well as phenolic oxygen. These facts indicate a four-coordination around metal. As all these complexes are diamagnetic, square-planar geometry is proposed for the complexes.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} chlorides (B.D.H.) were used. Distilled alcohol was used as solvent. The substituted salicylaldehydes were prepared by the reported method⁸.

Ligands were prepared by refluxing triazole and salicylaldehydes in 1 : 2 molar ratio in ethanolic medium for about 2 h and the resulting yellow solid was crystallized from ethanol. The complexes were prepared by refluxing a mixture of ethanolic solutions of the metal(II) chloride (0.01

mol) and the ligand (0.01 mol) for 3 h. The complexes separated were washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum over fused calcium chloride.

Metals were estimated gravimetrically as their sulfides. Nitrogen was estimated by microanalytical methods.

IR spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 1000 spectrophotometer and PMR spectra (DMSO) on a Bruke EM-390 spectrometer.

References

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